

Deliverable 13.4

Project website and social media

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Public – fully open	X
Sensitive - limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Deliverable type	(X)
R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC: Websites, patents, filing, press and media actions, videos, etc	X
OTHER: Software, technical diagram	
DMP: Data Management Plan	
DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc	

Revision			
Version	Date	Changed	Comments
1.0	15.04.2024		FINAL
1.1	20.12.2024	Disclaimer added	required in Article 17.3

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1 Introduction and summary

1.1 Purpose of the document

All actions along the project progress will be closely monitored, and based on it, targeted communication & dissemination measures will be taken to maximise the QUASAR impacts.

A project website will be released shortly and will be continuously updated with relevant information and updates around the project progress. It will include the dissemination activities from the partners.

It can be found here: <https://www.quasar-project.eu>

QUASAR can also be found on LinkedIn: [\(18\) QUASAR EU Horizon Project: Übersicht | LinkedIn](#)

2 Website

This tool will help the partners to disseminate about the progress of reaching the project goals, their participation to events and the publication of main results. Moreover, it will provide information about the consortium, the people and research teams involved and their specific expertise and work packages (in a section dedicated to the consortium).

The website will be updated regularly. Of course, the consent of all partners for proper will be necessary for good IPR management, following the rules described in the Consortium Agreement.

The structure of the website is currently composed of 5 sections which are listed and described below with some screen copies to illustrate.

This website is structured as follows:

2.1 Landing Page

MORE ABOUT THE PROJECT

- Our ambition
- Project Goal
- Approach
- Expected Results

Holistic Approach:

QUASAR aims to streamline EOL PV-module handling by:

- Engaging all stakeholders in the supply chain.
- Integrating diverse technologies and methodologies for collection and management.
- Utilizing reverse logistics, AI/machine learning, and digital twins for PLM.
- Adopting best practices in sorting, warehousing, testing, and repair/reuse.

[Learn More](#)

To achieve the objectives, QUASAR brings together a multidisciplinary consortium involving industrial players from the entire photovoltaic supply chain: photovoltaic module manufacturers, photovoltaic system operators, collectors, recyclers and end-users of secondary raw materials.

OBJECTIVES TO FULFIL

01

02

03

04

05

◀ ▶

Implement cost-efficient and transparent management processes and strategies for the entire EOL supply chain

- ◉ Identify raw material suitability from EOL-PV and addressable market volumes
- ◉ Assess and quantify decommissioning and repowering potential, related costs
- ◉ Optimize design and operation of EOL PV collection systems and EOL processing infrastructure, including transportation/logistics across the supply chain, based on cost and environmental impact

- ◉ Implement digital tracking solutions to facilitate reverse logistics
- ◉ Improve supply chain resilience (ability of a supply chain to respond to volatility)
- ◉ Contribute to harmonisation of standards and waste codes in the EOL-sector

[Learn More](#)

2.2 What we do

The visitor of the website will get more detailed information on the purpose of QUASAR, the main challenges in the field of EOL PV module handling and the new solutions to be developed through QUASAR. The work packages will be introduced, and a visualization will help the visitor to grasp the project holistic approach.

2.3 Who are we

The consortium can be discovered through an interactive map of the EU. It visualizes the involvement of 19 partners from 9 countries joining forces to deliver into the QUASAR project. By clicking on the company icon, each company and the people working on the project are presented. This section will be amended through the project life.

2.4 News & Events

This section gathers all the news related to the project; new publications, articles, consortium participation to events.

2.5 Library

Here the documents related to the project activities (papers, public deliverables...) will be made available to the public.

2.6 Contact

This last section allows to directly contact the consortium / coordinator.

The contact form is set against a dark blue background. On the left, there is a 'CONTACT US' button and a paragraph of text: 'Subscribe to our newsletter to stay updated on the latest trends, exclusive offers, and exciting news straight to your inbox. Join our community of enthusiasts and be the first to know about upcoming events, product launches, and special promotions. Don't miss out on valuable insights and content tailored just for you - sign up today and be part of our vibrant community!'. On the right, there are input fields for 'First Name', 'Last Name', and 'Email Address', followed by a larger 'Message' text area. Below the message area is a checkbox labeled 'I have read and agree to the Privacy Policy.' and a 'Submit' button.

2.7 Footer

The footnote contains the EU acknowledgment, to remind that this project was made possible thanks to the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation grant.

The footer section features the Quasar logo on the left. To its right are three columns of links: 'Navigation' (Who we are, News & Events, Library, Contact), 'Follow Us' (Instagram, LinkedIn), and 'Legal Information' (Privacy Policy, Terms and Conditions). At the bottom left is the European Union flag and the text: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement NO 101122298 "QUASAR"'. At the bottom right is the copyright notice: '©2024 QUASAR®'.

3 LinkedIn Page

Quasar can also be found on LinkedIn: (18) QUASAR EU Horizon Project: Übersicht | LinkedIn. It will share information from the website and from the consortium.

Suche

Start

Ihr Netzwerk

Jobs

Nachrichten

Mitteilung

QUASAR EU Horizon Project

Moving towards a sustainable future for the solar PV industry

Dienstleistungen für erneuerbare Energien · 58 Follower:innen · 11-50 Beschäftigte

 Maja & 6 weitere Kontakte folgen dieser Seite

 Nachricht

 Follower:in

Start

Info

Beiträge

Jobs

Personen

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Ihr Netzwerk

Jobs

Nachrichten

Mitteil

 QUASAR EU Horizon Project

Start

Info

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Info

The EU Horizon project QUASAR aims to enable a circular economy for the solar PV industry. 18 project partners from 9 countries will collect, treat, and upgrade solar panels that have reached their end of life, densify their value, and release them to serve as new products for solar energy and other purposes.

(70%plus eco-efficiency gains in the PV EOL supply chain by closed loop systems with enhanced recycling rates, systematic collection and management utilising digital twins)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement NO 101122298 "QUASAR"

[Alle Details anzeigen →](#)

4 Content and updates

As stated in the Description of Action, all partners are committed to write blogs for these tools, in order to generate a regular stream of new input. Every partner commits to writing (at least) 5 posts in the duration of the project. The project website will be maintained for a maximum of 3 years after the project end, with an option to transfer the domain to the Exploitation Manager or Project Coordinator if desired.

